

Cultivating Religious Culture Implementation

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ABSTRACT: As we all know, the current millennial generation is not surprised by technological sophistication. Children are getting smarter and smarter at using it, but the more open the ease of access to technology, the more worries arise. Technological openness is also accompanied by globalization, in which globalization is an individual or group phenomenon that influences each other in all aspects of life regardless of regional or national boundaries. The ease with which children currently access information (regional and international information) will certainly have an impact on the perspective of the person who consumes the information. It cannot be ensured that all the information that is spread is valid, including information in the religious or religious field.

The field of religion or religion is very sensitive to its influence on social life, because it involves the beliefs/beliefs of each individual. Therefore, with the increasing number of information in the field of religion that is spread, it must also be accompanied by the cultivation of religious cultural habits, especially for today's children. The inculcation of this religious culture can be done through institutions, organizations, as well as the habits of daily life in the family and society, as implemented at SMAN 1 Turen. Developments at SMAN 1 Turen are increasing rapidly both in terms of facilities, academic and non-academic achievements, in addition to developments in this regard, it is also accompanied by developments in the inculcation of culture or religious/religious habits in everyday school life. For example, SMAN 1 Turen holds a blessed Friday, recites Al-Kahfi letters and prays dhuha together, and commemorates other Islamic holidays with religious activities.

It should be noted that the inculcation of religious/religious culture is not only for SMAN 1 Turen residents who are Muslim, but also held for SMAN 1 Turen residents who are Christian with activities based on their respective beliefs. The implementation of these activities is to instill culture or religious habits in the students of SMAN 1 Turen, so that apart from improving student achievement in academic and non-academic fields which are mundane in nature, it is hoped that students will not be negligent with their God and the successful achievements that students get are a gift from God.

In implementing religious activities, the focus of this research is: how is the implementation in instilling religious culture at SMAN 1 Turen, whether the existence of religious culture planting activities at SMAN 1 Turen has a positive impact on students, and the expected output through the implementation of cultural planting religion at SMAN 1 Turen. This study uses a qualitative and descriptive research approach in the form of the type of reading studied. The type of research used is a case study that is carried out in an incentive, detailed, and in-depth manner towards a particular institution, organization, and group. Data collection procedures through interviews, observation, and documentation. Data analysis was carried out by data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion of the validity of the data using participation, persistence of observation, and, triangulations.

KEYWORDS: Implementation, Religious Culture, Output

INTRODUCTION

The condition of the world's development which is very rapid from various aspects brings positive and negative influences on human life. The positive impacts are definitely open to acceptance, but with various mobilizations of life which are a form of globalization of society, especially the millennial generation who are very aware of technological developments, they cannot be avoided and it is difficult to filter out the bad effects. It is not surprising that multidimensional conditions are increasingly complicated or complex, because along with world developments it is also easier to get access to incoming and outgoing culture and information from abroad which influences the social order of life.

Information from all sides of life spreads easily and its validation is difficult to distinguish, giving rise to positive and negative influences on people's views of the information sector consumed. There is nothing else that is very worrying about religious/religious life where if there is a deviation of views it will greatly affect all sides of social life, at this time there are already many elements carrying the name of a religion that adheres to beliefs contrary to true religious values.

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Things like that are what are feared to be persuasive to millennial children. In this case the world of education is one of the ways that society hopes for to guide children to the right understanding, because currently the world of education is experiencing a moral crisis, it is not uncommon for news to spread about deviations from life values that occur in schools and a lack of emphasis the formation of student character based on religious values, besides that education in schools tends to be only cognitive in nature so that students are only limited to memorizing material but are less embedded in psychomotor and the implementation of their character.

Even though basically in the world of education it is not only a matter of science being taught but the development of attitudes or character which refers to students' determination to practice the religious values that have been taught, which has actually been explained by the goals of national education written in Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System that: *"National education functions to develop capabilities and shape dignified national character and civilization in the context of educating the life of the nation, aiming at developing the potential of students to become human beings who believe and fear God Almighty, have noble character, are healthy, knowledgeable, capable, creative, independent, and become a democratic and responsible citizen."*

Referring to these educational goals, religious/religious education in schools is one of the efforts to make this happen, but this is not only done through material presentation, but there must be implementation/practice. With practice students will get the impression directly and from there that will grow the will or determination to do it in a sustainable manner based on the religious cultural values that have been taught, so that it will grow into a religious culture that has a positive impact in the lives of millennial children.

Regarding how important it is to inculcate religious culture or habits in students who are the next assets of the nation, it can be said that it is very important and very prioritized. The reason is that in one aspect of religion it includes all the values of life that should be carried out by all humans in order to create peace and prosperity. So whether or not students' habits are embedded that are based on religious values will affect the character and perspective of students' lives as well as the order of social life in the future. In the sense that in the future the movers of the nation will be them (students who are currently carrying out education), if a character based on religious values or the goals of national education that have been mentioned are not achieved, then can they become reliable captains to move the nation towards greater good? So that is a strong reason for the importance of planting religious culture in schools and its implementation.

According to Sahlan (2010: 116) "Religious culture is a set of religious values that underlies behavior, traditions, daily habits, and symbols practiced by school principals, teachers, administrative officers, students, and the school community." So one of the factors so that the cultivation of the implementation of religious culture in schools is successful is not only the students who are mobilized but all members of the school must also participate in practice, so that students will think that the existing educators and staff can be emulated and there is no jealousy in the eyes of students on the character or attitude of educators and other staff.

RESEARCH METHODS

This research uses a descriptive qualitative research approach which is an in-depth, detailed and continuous observation of the object to be studied using a case study approach. The data taken comes from observation, interviews, and documentation and then processed by presentation, reduction, drawing conclusions to check the validity in detail, observation and triangulation. The object of this study is located at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency, East Java. In statistical data, population is data that has something in common with the object to be studied (object of inference). ". The population in this study were all teachers and staff and students who participated in efforts to inculcate the implementation of religious culture at Turen 1 Public High School. Arikunto (2010) says that "Samples are part or representative of the population being studied. To determine the size of the sample, if there are less than 100 subjects, it is better to take all of them so that the research is population research. "If the subject is bigger, it can be taken between 10%-15% or 20%-25% or more." (Arikunto, 2002:109). In this study, samples were taken from 10 people consisting of teachers and staff, and 100 students.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data obtained comes from observations and interviews with school principals, teachers, employees, and students at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency and is equipped with various related data documents as a focus in research that can be described systematically related to planting. Implementation of religious culture at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency.

1. Implementation in instilling religious culture at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency

Before entering into its implementation, it is necessary to first understand the nature or meaning of religious culture. Religious culture is formed from two words, namely "Culture and Religion". According to KBBI, culture is a thought/custom/something that has become a habit that is difficult to change. As for the understanding of culture, according to several experts, one of them is Andreas Eppink "Culture is social values, ethics, knowledge, and knowledge that are systematically arranged as a characteristic of every person or group." Quoted from Wikipedia "Culture is a way of life that develops and is owned by a person or group of people

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and is passed down from generation to generation but not hereditary." It can be concluded that "Culture is a pattern or way of life in the form of social values, ethics, behavior, or other activities that grow in society and become habits and then become a characteristic of life in a group or society and are difficult to change.

Religious according to KBBI "Religious is religious/religious in nature" religion itself is belief in God; belief (animism and dynamism); religion. According to Umi Mashitoh "Religiousness is an attitude and behavior that obeys in carrying out the teachings of the religion one adheres to, tolerance towards the implementation of other religious worship and living in harmony with adherents of other religions". Religious is anything or activity or behavior or attitude that reflects the implementation of the values taught in religion that every human being believes in. In this case the values taught in religion are not only about rituals or worship or how to worship God, but also teach about the morals that should be owned by humans who live in the world and live in social society (So apart from Islam, apart from teachings about praying and praying, Religion also includes the attitude or behavior of loving one another because we feel that we are both creatures of Allah SWT, being tolerant and respectful of each other, and of course not doing things that can hurt other people based on the teachings of Islam).

Religious culture is a way of life or habits of a group or society whose behavior or activities reflect the teachings of the religion they adhere to (and in this case is the religion of Islam) and of course there is a purpose. In religion and almost all religions teach the same value of life it's just that the way of believing in God or worship is different, all religions teach their people not to act criminally that will hurt or kill fellow human beings, all teach to respect and respect each other in order to create prosperity in life world, all also teach to always remember God based on their respective beliefs so that humans in living their lives can be controlled. That is what is expected with the creation of a religious culture in life.

In order for this religious culture to always be implemented and not eroded by the freedom of the times, it is necessary to instill religious culture from an early age, as was done at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency, which first held a routine blessing Friday event by distributing food to road users, especially for workers such as pedicab drivers, motorcycle taxi drivers, street vendors, etc., the food is obtained from Friday alms for students and teachers of SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency with the intention of implementing religious values, namely loving each other, helping each other, and sharing with others man. The second activity is to carry out dhuha prayers and read al-Kahfi in congregation every Friday in the Hall of SMAN 1 Turen as a form of implementation of religious teachings to always remember and pray to Allah SWT. Third, every morning the teacher welcomes the arrival of students at the entrance gate to give greetings and greetings that aim to instill the habit of polite soap to students. Fourthly, it requires students of SMAN 1 Turen to carry out midday prayers in congregation with the absence of fingerprints with the aim that even though some time students will pray in congregation because they are forced to be absent, at least the school is making efforts to form the determination of students to carry out their obligations, this also aims to form the character of students who are responsible for their obligations or duties. Fifth, of course, SMAN 1 Turen never leaves activities or events to commemorate Islamic holidays by holding events or activities according to the theme of the holidays, this is done with the aim of giving lessons to students regarding the history of Islamic holidays which are full of struggles. in the name and obtain the blessing of Allah SWT.

With this implementation activity the students of SMAN 1 Turen were very enthusiastic, because direct field practice made it an effort to carry out learning activities that were not boring and in this way the students would get a distinct impression. Polite behavior not only in the school environment, but with Friday blessing activities (distribution of food to people outside the school environment) also requires courtesy so that other people who are given feel valued as well as students will feel happy if other people want to accept student gifts with pleasure. In addition, students who are used to worshiping Allah (congregational prayers, Duha prayers, reading the Koran) will foster feelings of love and fear of Allah so that the students of SMAN 1 Turen will always carry out the orders and prohibitions of Allah SWT.

2. The positive impact/change seen in students after the activity of instilling the implementation of religious culture at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency

Activities that have been programmed by SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency aim to familiarize students with the implementation of religious culture to show changes in a positive direction towards students' attitudes or behavior. Quoted from the official website of SMAN 1 Turen which states that the Friday blessing activity has entered its second week, this proves the enthusiasm of school members including students to carry out social activities based on religious/religious values and proves that they can be invited to commit to carrying out the mission of implementing culture. or religious habits in the school environment.

The program that was held by SMAN 1 Turen also led to a new program formed by the BDI (Islamic Dakwah Agency) organization SMAN 1 Turen to participate in promoting the implementation of religious culture by inviting all Muslim students to read al-Waqiah letter every Monday morning and Yasin letters every Friday morning. Even though in this activity students who are millennial children are less oriented towards understanding the meaning of suat al-Waqiah and Yasin itself, this is an attempt by educators to raise thoughts in students regarding "Why should I do this? Is it fadhilah or benefit if I get used to reading this?" so that by bringing up thoughts like that in the minds of students it will move students to find out the benefits of programs organized by the school, it is hoped that after knowing the benefits it will grow into habits and become entrenched in the environment of

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students (millennial youth) related to attitudes or behavior or activities that are religious or appropriate with the values taught in Islam.

3. Output from implementation activities instilling religious culture at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency

The output or result of a goal or vision of instilling the implementation of religious culture at SMAN 1 Turen is of course in the form of programs or activities as previously explained. From a subjective perspective, there are several outputs resulting from promoting the implementation of religious culture at SMAN 1 Turen, namely:

a. Active BDI (Islamic Da'wah Agency) SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency

SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency, which has the goal of forming student character through socio-religious activities, the policy is not only from one party (superior only) but does not forget to embrace BDI SMAN 1 Turen as an organization with a religious spirit. By embracing the BDI organization, it will bridge the gap between all students of SMAN 1 Turen and teachers/students regarding the activities being held. By involving the BDI organization, those who join the BDI organization feel more enthusiastic about socializing or preaching about Islamic religious values to other students (friends), besides that they are also enthusiastic about implementing their work program because they receive full support from the school.

b. Students of SMAN 1 Turen who have good morals or manners

Through programs to inculcate the implementation of religious culture which are accustomed to at SMAN 1 Turen, of course it has indirectly given birth to students who have noble character, by getting used to helping each other, giving each other in the school environment, also giving birth to a similar character when students/ students are in an environment outside the school, especially with regard to mutual respect, courtesy, tolerance, and mutual help.

c. Establish closeness between teachers and students so as to facilitate collaboration in teaching and learning activities

When the implementation of religious culture activities takes place, of course, it also involves all students of SMAN 1 Turen and their teachers. During the activity, it will lead to semi-formal communication between students and teachers so that students feel comfortable and are heard by the teacher when expressing their opinions. Through field practice activities the teacher can examine the character of students in learning, then usually offers of learning methods that are adapted to the character and desires of students so that the materials and values that need to be conveyed by the teacher can be conveyed perfectly or in full to students. In general, building closeness between teachers and students also makes it easier for teachers/educators to instill positive character in students because when students feel they have an emotional closeness with the teacher, then students feel comfortable and their opinions are listened to by the teacher, students will be more obedient to orders, prohibitions, and the teachings given by the teacher.

CONCLUSION

In the era of freedom of mobilization of life as a result of globalization, it is very important to inculcate habits that implement religious culture from an early age, indefinitely, as was done at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency. Due to the increasingly free foreign cultural influences entering the country as a result of globalization increasingly affecting lifestyles and human perspectives on the values of life, if a straight/correct understanding is not instilled from an early age it is feared that the minds of millennial children today are easily indoctrinated with culture, information, and understandings that are contrary to the truth and teachings of religion (in this case the religion of Islam), none other than currently many are spreading teachings that are contrary to the teachings of the religion of Islam but claiming to carry the names of the religion of Islam. Apart from that, globalization is accompanied by the acculturation of foreign cultures that enter Indonesia, where foreign culture carries an attitude of liberalism and individualism, this is very influential in changing the ethics or behavior of the millennial generation in Indonesia, if you can't filter it, it will fade away. -children towards their parents and also in social activities. The attitude of individualism will turn children into not caring about others or giving rise to selfish attitudes in children.

Changes like these are what are feared will widen among young people today, therefore nowadays children spend 8 hours at school, so it is a big hope for parents that school/education can be one of the efforts to prevent the impact bad from globalization and being a place to instill positive character in children/students so as to create the implementation of religious culture among young people both within the school environment and outside the school environment.

As implemented at SMAN 1 Turen, Turen District, Malang Regency, the school feels that apart from being responsible for transferring knowledge or conveying scientific material according to the curriculum, the school is also aware that school is a place for student character formation, where students who are in the search for identity phase himself, then he must be guided in a positive direction, and help show the extent of the world regarding positive and negative influences on the free mobilization of life and also directed to filter out things that will have a negative impact. None other than all of this is planned to produce quality, moral, and cultured human resources in accordance with religious values or those taught in Islam to create prosperity in social life.

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